

Decolourisation of Oils with Mixed Adsorbents.

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Pure inorganic adsorbents such as silica gel, aluminium and ferric hydroxides etc., are characterised by inertness to many chemicals, non-inflammability and capability of easy regeneration; but they suffer from the disadvantage that their activity as decolourising agents for mineral and vegetable oils is comparatively low. Attempts have been made in the past by various investigators to improve the activity of inorganic adsorbents. Thus Patrick and others (Patrick and McGavack *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 42, 946; Munro and Johnson, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1925, 17, 88; Wood, Shelley and Trusty, *ibid* 1926, 18, 169) have studied the optimum conditions for the preparation of silica and other gels. Siliceous decolourisers of high activity have also been obtained by the treatment of suitable earths with inorganic acids (Koetschsau, *Z. angew. Chem.*, 1926, 39, 210). A new principle for the preparation of suitable adsorbents has been followed by some investigators (E.P. 243123, 255904; Reyerson, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1927, 31, 88) who incorporated catalytic substances such as copper, nickel and platinum, etc., with silica and other inorganic gels. It is claimed that these mixed masses are highly suitable both as catalysers and as adsorbents of high activity.

In a previous paper (Chowdhury and Bagchi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 111) it has been shown that specially prepared mixed adsorbents consisting of alumina and silica gels have much higher activity for removal of sulphur compounds, than either of the constituents separately. This result has received confirmation in the work of Chowdhury and Pal (published in this issue) who have shown that silicalised bauxite has a higher adsorptive capacity for benzol vapour than either bauxite or silica alone. It is here intended to extend the above observations to the decolourisation of mineral and vegetable oils and to the preparation of suitable mixed adsorbents for the purpose. In the following investigations, pure silica gel has been prepared by the method of Patrick (*loc. cit.*), and alumina gel by the method of precipitating the gel from aluminium sulphate solution by ammonia. The principle for the preparation and activation of mixed adsorbents is the same as that followed by Chowdhury and Bagchi (*loc. cit.*), except that in a few instances the method of drying has been modified.

The decolourisation tests were carried out as follows:—100 c.c. of the oil (coloured kerosene and groundnut oils) were taken in a glass stoppered bottle and shaken mechanically with different amounts of

decolourisers (freshly dried) for different lengths of time, the colour being measured after each experiment with tintometers.

Measurement of Colour.—The Lovibond tintometer was used for the purpose. Attempts were at first made to use the Dubosque type of colorimeter, in which a known thickness of the original oil was matched with carefully measured depths of the decolourised (treated) oil. It was however found that the two columns of oil could never be satisfactorily matched. The colour of the original and the treated oils not being identical, it is evident that the original colour is not due to any single substance, but to a mixture of substances of different colours. Owing to the specific nature of all adsorbents, these coloured substances are removed to a different degree by each decolouriser, so that the treated oil gets a different shade of colour from that of the original. A satisfactory method of measuring decolourisation must, therefore, take into account the different degree of removal of the component colours. The Lovibond tintometer was found satisfactory for the purpose. It is true as Parsons and Wilson (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1922, 14, 269) have pointed out that Lovibond colour units are not additive and subtractive in the strictest mathematical sense. But it has also been shown by those investigators that up to 50°L (Lovibond), there is practically no deviation from the true colour as measured by them. In the following investigations no glass above 20°L, has been used and the question of any appreciable error does not therefore arise. We have used $\frac{1}{2}$ " cell for kerosene and 1" cell for groundnut oil in the colour measurements. Both the original and the treated oils have been satisfactorily matched against a combination of red and yellow glasses. The percentage of colour removed has been calculated as follows:—If a be the sum of the numbers of glasses of any particular shade required to match against the original oil and b the sum of the numbers of glasses of the same shade required to match the treated oil of the same thickness, then the percentage removal of colour is given by $100(a-b)/a$.

Comparison of the Efficiency of different Adsorbents.—The usual practice is to shake 100 c.c. of a coloured oil with a fixed amount (5 g.) of the different adsorbents and to measure the colour of the treated oil with a tintometer. When the Lovibond tintometer is used for the purpose, the comparative efficiencies of the adsorbents used are calculated as follows:—Suppose the colour of the original oil is 30°L, and those of the portions treated with two adsorbents A and B are 15°L and 10°L respectively. The colour removed by

A is therefore $(90^\circ - 15^\circ)L$ and that removed by the same amount of B is $20^\circ L$. Hence the efficiency of A to that of B is assumed to be as 15:20. Hence, it is assumed that 4 g. of A would effect the same degree of decolourisation as 3 g. of B. A reference to the curves in Figs. 1A and 1B obtained by plotting amounts of adsorbents along X-axis, and percentage removal of colour along Y-axis, will show that this assumption is inaccurate and does not agree with the actual experimental data. It will also be observed that the decolourisation of kerosene with large amounts of the mixed adsorbent, alumina-silica, is greater than with the corresponding amounts of bone charcoal, but the case is different when the amounts of the adsorbents are small. This fact and the different degree of bendings in the curves for different adsorbents clearly show that the assumption of a constant efficiency ratio between two adsorbents is untenable.

Fig. IA.

Composition of different adsorbents for red colour.

I - Bauxite ; II - Bauxite-silica II ; III - Alumina-silica V ; IV - Alumina-silica, II ; V - Alumina-silica III ; VI - Bone charcoal.

Fig. IB.

Comparison of different adsorbents for yellow colour.

I=Bauxite; II=Bauxite-silica II; III=Alumina-silica V; IV=Alumina-silica I; V=Alumina-silica III; VI=Bone charcoal.

Another method for the comparison of adsorbents is to treat an oil with different amounts of adsorbents until the filtered oils show the same colour in a colorimeter. The practical difficulties in regulating the quantities of adsorbents until the same colour is obtained are great, as the colour can only be measured after filtration following each treatment. Hence this method finds little favour in actual practice.

The best means of comparing the efficiencies is to draw complete decolourisation curves with different amounts of adsorbents. From a reference to such curves (Fig. I, A and B) the quantities of the adsorbents to effect the same degree of decolourisation or the degree of decolourisation effected by the same amounts of adsorbents may easily be found. It will be further observed that the steeper the slope of a curve for smaller quantities of an adsorbent, the better the adsorbent when used as a decolouriser.

The activities of different adsorbents on coloured kerosene (sample no. 1) may be compared from the following tables and the corresponding graphs in Fig. I, A and B.

TABLE IA.

Comparison of different adsorbents (for red colour).

Vol. of kerosene no. 1 = 100 c.c. having red colour = 2.7°L and yellow colour = 18.5°L.

Adsorbent in g.	<i>Bauxite.</i>		<i>Bauxite-silica mixture II.</i>		<i>Bone charcoal.</i>	
	Colour observed.	Removal of colour.	Colour observed.	Removal of colour.	Colour observed.	Removal of colour.
1	—	—	—	—	1.1°L	59.26%
2	—	—	1.8°L	40.74%	0.9	66.67
5	2.15°L	20.37%	1.0	62.96	0.8	70.37
10	1.9	29.63	0.62	77.03	0.7	74.07
20	1.65	38.89	0.42	84.44	—	—
30	1.6	40.74	—	—	—	—
	<i>Alumina-silica mixture II.</i>		<i>Alumina-silica mixture III.</i>		<i>Alumina-silica mixture V.</i>	
1	1.65	38.89	1.5	44.44	1.75	85.19
2	1.2	55.56	0.92	65.93	1.35	50.00
5	0.65	75.93	0.82	77.03	0.82	69.63
10	0.49	84.07	0.35	87.03	0.5	81.48

TABLE IB.

Comparison of different adsorbents (for yellow colour).

(Data observed in simultaneous measurements with Table IA.)

Adsorbent in g.	<i>Bauxite.</i>		<i>Bauxite-silica mixture II.</i>		<i>Bone charcoal.</i>	
	Colour observed.	Removal of colour.	Colour observed.	Removal of colour.	Colour observed.	Removal of colour.
1	—	—	—	—	8.0°L	51.52%
2	—	—	12.0°L	27.27%	6.6	60.00
5	14.2°L	13.94%	9.8	40.61	4.5	72.73
10	13.0	21.21	7.0	57.58	3.8	76.97
20	11.8	28.48	5.0	69.70	—	—
30	11.3	31.52	—	—	—	—
	<i>Alumina-silica mixture II.</i>		<i>Alumina-silica mixture III.</i>		<i>Alumina-silica mixture V.</i>	
1	11.3	31.52	10.8	34.55	13.0	21.21
2	9.8	40.61	8.8	45.87	10.8	34.55
5	7.1	56.97	6.6	60.0	7.76	53.94
10	5.5	66.67	4.5	72.73	5.0	69.70

The adsorption curves for pure alumina and silica are not shown above. Decolourisation with these materials is slight and is of the same order as that observed with bauxite. It will be observed from the figures given above that the adsorption of red and yellow colours are not identical. In some cases more red is adsorbed while in others more yellow, exactly as is to be expected from the well known specific nature of adsorbents.

Incidentally the above tables furnish figures for testing the applicability of Freundlich's equation

$$\frac{x}{m} = kc^n \quad \text{or} \quad \log x \cdot m = \log k + 1/n \log c.$$

where x = amount of colour removed separately for each component colour red or yellow;

m = grams of adsorbent used for 100 c.c. of oil;

c = amount of colour remaining in the solution after adsorption;

and k and n are constants dependent upon the solution and the adsorbent used.

The following table gives the values for $\log x/m$ and $\log c$, as calculated from the data of the previous table. The difference between the observed colour and the original colour has been taken as x , c being obviously the observed colour.

TABLE IIA (for red colour).

The values deduced from corresponding figures of Table IA (for red colour).

Adsorbent in g.	<i>Bauxite.</i>		<i>Bauxite-silica mixture II.</i>		<i>Bone charcoal.</i>	
	$\log x/m.$	$\log c.$	$\log x/m.$	$\log c.$	$\log x/m.$	$\log c.$
1	—	—	—	—	0.2041	0.0414
2	—	—	-0.2596	0.2041	-0.0458	-0.0458
5	-0.9596	0.3224	-0.4685	0.0000	-0.4202	-0.0989
10	-1.0969	0.2788	-0.6819	-0.2076	-0.6990	-0.1549
20	-1.2798	0.2175	-0.9431	-0.3768	—	—
30	-1.4858	0.2041	—	—	—	—

TABLE IIA—*continued*.

Adsorbent in g.	<i>Alumina-silica mixture II.</i>		<i>Alumina-silica mixture III.</i>		<i>Alumina-silica mixture V.</i>	
	log x/m .	log c .	log x/m .	log c .	log x/m .	log c .
1	0·0212	0·2175	0·0792	0·1761	-0·0223	0·3430
2	-0·1249	0·0792	-0·0506	-0·0362	-0·1707	0·1303
5	-0·3872	-0·1871	-0·3809	-0·2076	-0·4248	-0·0862
10	-0·6440	-0·3665	-0·8259	-0·4559	-0·6576	-0·3010

TABLE IIB (for yellow colour).

The values deduced from the corresponding figures of Table IB (for yellow colour).

Adsorbent in g.	<i>Bauxite.</i>		<i>Bauxite-silica mixture II.</i>		<i>Bone charcoal.</i>	
	log x/m .	log c .	log x/m .	log c .	log x/m .	log c .
1	—	—	—	—	0·9294	0·9081
2	—	—	0·3522	1·0762	0·6946	0·8195
5	-0·3372	1·1523	0·1271	0·9912	0·3902	0·6592
10	-0·4559	1·1189	-0·0223	0·8451	0·1038	0·5798
20	-0·8289	1·0719	-0·2403	0·6990	—	—
30	-0·7612	1·0591	—	—	—	—

Adsorbent in g.	<i>Alumina-silica mixture II.</i>		<i>Alumina-silica mixture III.</i>		<i>Alumina-silica mixture V.</i>	
	log x/m .	log c .	log x/m .	log c .	log x/m .	log c .
1	0·7160	1·0591	0·7559	1·0834	0·5441	1·1130
2	0·5250	0·9912	0·5855	0·9445	0·4543	1·0394
5	0·2742	0·8513	0·2967	0·8195	0·2504	0·8808
10	0·0414	0·7404	0·0792	0·6532	0·0607	0·6990

To test the general applicability of mixed decolourisers in conformity with Freundlich's rule a different sample of kerosene oil was treated with varying amounts of adsorbents. Results are given in the following table.

TABLE IIC.

Adsorbent used—Alumina-silica mixture II.
 Vol. of kerosene sample no. II=100 c.c.
 Original colour—red=1·0°L and yellow=20°L.

Adsorbent in g.	Red colour.			Yellow colour.		
	Colour observed.	$\log x/m.$	$\log c.$	Colour observed.	$\log x/m.$	$\log c.$
1	1·2°L	-0·3979	0·0792	15°L	0·6990	1·1761
2	1·0	-0·6229	0·0000	13	0·5441	1·1189
5	0·72	-0·7545	-0·1427	9·8	0·3096	0·9912
10	0·50	-0·9586	-0·3010	7·6	0·0934	0·8308

Fig. II.

Adsorption isotherm for red.

I—Bauxite ; II—Bone charcoal ; III—Alumina-silica II ;
 IV—Bauxite-silica II ; V—Alumina-silica V ; VI—Alumina-silica II
 VII—Alumina-silica III.

It will be seen from the curves (Fig. II) that only straight lines are obtained by plotting $\log x/m$ against $\log c$. The values of $1/n$, that is, the tangents of the angles of inclination of the curves to the $\log c$ -axis are found to be greater than unity (because no angle is less than 45°). In the general adsorption phenomena the values of $1/n$ are less than unity. Such high figures for $1/n$ in the case of decolourisation of oils have also been observed by Rogers, Grimm and Lemmon (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1926, 18, 164). Unlike the general rule, the amount of colouring matters adsorbed in this case, is proportional to c (colour concentration) raised to a power greater than unity. Freundlich's equation is therefore applicable in the adsorption of both red and yellow components of the colour of kerosene only with this modification. The fact that the amount adsorbed is proportional to c raised to a power greater than unity, explains clearly why it is so very difficult to remove the last traces of colour from kerosene by the method of adsorption in actual practice.

Another significance of the log-curves may be noted. The higher the efficiency of a decolouriser the more upward parallel displacement its log-curve experiences. This gives a good picture for comparative decolourising efficiencies of adsorbents.

Velocity of Decolourisation.—In the previous experiments the oil was shaken with decolourisers until the colouring matter was no more adsorbed. It is however desirable to investigate the time required to attain the equilibrium by different adsorbents. The following tables give the data of experiments with this end in view. The rate of shaking, size of particles, etc., have been kept constant. The influence of temperature in the case of solid-liquid interface being only slight for small variations of temperature, the necessity of a thermostat was dispensed with and the experiments were conducted at room temperature. It will be observed that the equilibrium is mostly attained in $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours. The time of contact in all experiments has been kept at 2 hours in order to ensure complete adsorption in each case. The nature of the curves (Fig. III) is similar to those usually found for adsorption velocity curves (Freundlich, "Colloid and Capillary Chemistry," p. 109), although the equilibrium is attained after a comparatively long time and not in seconds or minutes.

Velocity of adsorption.

Fig. III.

I=Bauxite-silica III (yellow). II=Bauxite-silica III (red).
 III=Bauxite-silica II (yellow). IV=Bauxite-silica II (red).

TABLE IIIA.

Velocity of adsorption.

Adsorbent—Bauxite-silica mixture II (21.88% SiO_2): 2 g. for 100 c.c. kerosene no. I.

Colour—red = 2.7°L and yellow = 16.5°L.

Time of shaking.	<i>Red colour.</i>		<i>Yellow colour.</i>	
	Colour observed.	Colour removed per g. of adsorbent.	Colour observed.	Colour removed per g. of adsorbent.
10 mins.	1.9°L	14.82%	14.2°L	8.97%
20 ..	1.87	15.37	18.0	10.61
40 ..	1.72	18.15	12.5	12.12
60 ..	1.65	19.44	12.0	13.64
90 ..	1.60	20.37	"	"
2 hrs.	"	"	"	"
4 ..	"	"	"	"

TABLE IIIB.

Adsorbent—Bauxite-silica mixture III (90.8% SiO_2): 4 g. per 100 c.c. kerosene no. I.

Time of shaking.	<i>Red colour.</i>		<i>Yellow colour.</i>	
	Colour observed.	Colour removed per g. of adsorbent.	Colour observed.	Colour removed per g. of adsorbent.
5 mins.	2.15°L	5.09%	14.8°L	2.58%
10 ..	2.00	6.48	14.2	3.48
20 ..	1.90	7.41	13.0	5.30
40 ..	1.8	8.33	12.5	6.06
1 hr.	1.72	9.07	"	"
1½ hrs.	"	"	12.0	6.82
2 ..	1.6	10.19	"	"
4 ..	"	"	"	"

Relation between Composition and Activity of Mixed Adsorbents.—

It will be observed from Tables IIIA, and IIIB, that the relative proportions of the constituents in silicalised bauxite affect the degree of decolourisation to a great extent. Similar observations have also been made by Chowdhury and Bagchi and by Chowdhury and Pal (*loc. cit.*). It is therefore necessary to find out the most suitable composition of mixed decolourisers and to test their activities both for mineral and vegetable oils. The mixed decolourisers investigated are:—

1. Bauxite—silica;
2. Alumina—silica;
3. Carbon—alumina.

Mixed adsorbents have been prepared, by the precipitation of one adsorbent upon another suspended in finely divided form.

Preparation of the Mixed Adsorbents.

1. *Silicalised Bauxite.*

The bauxite used gave the following figures:— Al_2O_3 , 59.2; Fe_2O_3 , 3.8; SiO_2 , 19.2; TiO_2 , 3.7; moisture, 11.8 per cent.; Ca, traces; Mg, traces.

For the preparation of silicalised bauxite of different compositions, the bauxite was finely powdered, and suspended in the usual

manner in a 4.94 per cent. solution of sodium silicate, the silica precipitated with a 10 per cent. solution of hydrochloric acid under constant stirring (mechanical), filtered and washed thoroughly. The different adsorbents thus obtained were pressed, dried in the air and subsequently at 60°, in a steam oven. This mode of drying has been found to be particularly suitable for the preparation of the mixed adsorbents, as well as of the pure gels. The adsorbents were used for decolourisation in the form of fine granules (80-160 mesh per sq. inch) after the final activation at suitable temperatures in a furnace, in the presence of a current of dry air so as to reduce their water-content to a suitable percentage.

The percentages of silica (deposited) as found on analysis of the mixtures and their moisture contents are shown in the following table which contains figures to show the relationship between composition and activity of the mixed bauxite-silica adsorbents.

TABLE IV.

Decolourisation with silicalised bauxite of different compositions.

Adsorbent used—5 g. for 100 c. c. kerosene no. I, of red colour = 2.7°L, and yellow colour = 16.5°L. Time of shaking = 2 hrs.

No. of mixture.	Percentage composition of mixtures.			Red colour.		Yellow colour.	
	Bauxite.	Silica.	Moisture.	Colour obs.	Colour removed.	Colour obs.	Colour removed.
I	100%	—	9.78%	2.15°L	20.37%	14.2°L	13.94%
I	89.91	10.09%	9.76	1.9	29.63	13.0	21.21
II	78.12	21.88	9.23	1.0	62.96	9.8	40.61
III	69.18	30.82	8.8	1.6	40.74	11.3	31.52
IV	64.1	35.9	9.1	1.72	36.29	12.0	27.27
V	54.36	45.64	9.26	1.9	29.63	13.0	21.21
VI	37.32	62.68	8.77	1.9	29.63	12.5	24.24
VII	26.31	73.69	7.94	1.87	30.74	11.3	31.52
—	—	100.	6.0	2.15	20.37	13.0	21.21

The increase in the figures for decolourisation is remarkable, the maximum results being obtained with 21.88 per cent. silica. A mere mechanical mixture of the two decolourisers has no increased efficiency, as individually both of them have but poor decolourising

power. That the observed increase in efficiency of the mixed adsorbents is not due to a slight variation of the water contents from mixture to mixture will find confirmation from the data given in a subsequent section for the effect of moisture contents of the decolourisers. A clear picture of the variation of efficiency of the mixed adsorbents will be obtained with reference to the curves of Fig. IV. A reference to Fig. I, A and B, will show what a great increase in activity, hauxite has undergone by the addition of 21.88 per cent. of silica.

Decolourisation of kerosene with silicalised bauxite of different composition.

Fig. IV.

2. Alumina-silica Mixtures.

For the preparation of alumina-silica mixtures of different compositions, undried silica gel was suspended in a 10 per cent. solution of aluminium sulphate and aluminium hydroxide was precipitated with ammonia under constant stirring (mechanical). Washing the gels free from acid, drying, activation etc., were similar to those described above for mixed bauxite-silica adsorbents. The percentage composition as found on analysis and water-content of different

gel-mixtures are shown in the following tables, giving data for the variation of efficiency of the mixed adsorbents with composition.

TABLE VA.

Decolourisation with mixed alumina-silica adsorbents of different compositions.

Adsorbent used—2 g. per 100 c.c. kerosene no. I, of red colour = 2.7°L, and yellow colour = 16.5°L.

No. of mixture.	Composition of mixtures.			Red colour.		Yellow colour.	
	Silica.	Alumina.	Moisture.	Colour obs.	Colour removal.	Colour obs.	Colour removal.
—	100%	—	6.0%	2.5°L	7.41%	15.0°L	9.09%
I	94.04	5.96%	7.23	1.6	40.74	10.8	34.55
II	90.01	9.99	5.81	1.2	55.56	9.8	40.61
III	83.23	16.77	7.46	0.92	65.93	8.8	46.70
IV	74.87	25.13	6.33	1.2	55.56	10.3	37.58
V	63.3	36.7	5.25	1.35	50.00	10.8	34.55
VI	63.1	36.9	4.89	1.35	50.00	10.8	34.55
VII	53.26	46.74	7.83	1.6	40.74	10.8	34.55
VIII	53.21	46.79	5.72	1.6	40.74	11.05	33.03
IX	23.21	76.79	6.12	1.72	36.29	12.0	27.27
—	—	100	7.64	2.27	15.93	15.0	9.09

TABLE VB.

Decolourisation with mixed alumina-silica adsorbents of different composition.

Adsorbent used—5 g. per 100 c.c. groundnut oil no. I, of red colour = 1.72°L and yellow colour = 12.5°L.

No. of mixture.	Composition of mixtures.			Red colour.		Yellow colour.	
	Silica.	Alumina.	Moisture.	Colour obs.	Colour removal.	Colour obs.	Colour removal.
—	100%	—	6.0%	1.72°L	—	12.5°L	—
II	90.01	9.99%	5.81	1.40	18.6%	8.8	23.6%
III	83.23	16.77	7.46	1.35	21.51	7.6	39.2
IV	74.87	25.13	6.33	1.4	18.6	9.8	21.6
VI	63.1	36.9	4.89	1.5	12.79	10.8	18.6
VIII	53.21	46.79	5.72	1.6	6.98	11.3	9.6
IX	23.21	76.79	6.12	1.65	4.07	12.0	4.0
—	—	100	7.64	1.65	4.07	12.5	—

Decolourisation with mixed alumina-silica of different composition.

Fig. V.

I = Removal of red in kerosene no. I, using 2 g. adsorbent per 100 c.c.
 II = " yellow " " " " "
 III = " " groundnut oil " 5 g. " "
 IV = " red " " " " "

While either silica or alumina is but a poor decolouriser for kerosene oil and particularly so for groundnut oil, quite a striking increase in the activity has been obtained from intimate mixtures of the two. The data of the above tables, plotted in Fig. V, manifest this fact in a clear manner. The maximum efficiency is reached both for kerosene and groundnut oil in the mixture III containing 83.3 per cent. silica and 16.67 per cent. alumina. It is interesting to note that the order of efficiency of the different mixed adsorbents is strictly maintained in the decolourisation of both kerosene and groundnut oil. It will be observed from the curves that besides the optimum mixture other mixtures of composition varying over a large range have remarkable increase in activity over that of the pure silica or alumina. A reference to the curves in Fig. I, A and B, for different alumina-silica mixtures and bone charcoal, will show that the mixed adsorbent alumina-silica III (optimum mixture) is of the same order of efficiency as bone charcoal and the other mixtures also are not much inferior to it. These mixed adsorbents

have on the other hand many advantages over bone charcoal such as those usually claimed for the most inorganic adsorbents.

3. Activated Carbon-alumina Mixtures.

The method of preparation and activation is the same as in the case of alumina-silica mixtures, except that activated carbon (Kahlbaum) was suspended in the aluminium sulphate solution.

The results obtained for the decolourisation of kerosene and groundnut oil are given in the following table.

TABLE VIA.

Decolourisation with mixed carbon-alumina adsorbents of different compositions.

Adsorbent used—2 g. per 100 c.c. kerosene no. II, of red colour = 1·6°L and yellow colour = 20°L.

No. of mixtures.	Composition.		Red colour.		Yellow colour.	
	Carbon.	Alumina.	Colour obs.	Removal of colour.	Colour obs.	Removal of colour.
—	100%	—	0·70°L	56·25%	10·3°L	48·5%
I	92·7	7·3%	0·62	61·25	10·3	48·5
II	86·7	13·3	0·62	61·25	10·3	48·5
III	67·2	32·8	0·62	46·75	11·3	43·5
IV	38·4	61·6	0·92	42·50	13·0	35·0
V	25·2	74·8	1·00	37·5	13·5	32·5
—	—	100	1·4	12·5	18·0	10·0

TABLE VIB.

Decolourisation with mixed carbon-alumina adsorbents of different compositions.

Adsorbent used—5 g. per 100 c.c. groundnut oil no. II of red colour = 1·6°L and yellow colour = 6·6°L.

No. of mixtures.	Composition.		Red colour.		Yellow colour.	
	Carbon.	Alumina.	Colour obs.	Removal of colour.	Colour obs.	Removal of colour.
—	100%	—	0·8%	50·0%	2·2°L	66·67%
I	92·7	7·3%	0·8	50·0	2·2	66·67
II	86·7	13·3	0·8	50·0	2·2	66·67
III	67·2	32·8	0·85	46·88	2·3	66·67
IV	38·2	61·6	1·1	31·25	2·8	57·58
V	25·2	74·8	1·85	15·63	5·0	24·24
—	—	100	1·6	—	6·0	2·00

In the case of activated carbon-alumina mixtures the increase over the efficiency of carbon is rather slight, but it will be observed that quite a large percentage (about 30%) of costly activated carbon may easily be replaced by alumina without loss of efficiency. The activity is however always more than that calculated from the composition of a mechanical mixture of the two adsorbents on the supposition that the activity of each adsorbent is independent of the other. This increase is more remarkable when alumina predominates in the mixtures. The coating of alumina on the surface of carbon has the further advantage as observed by Berl (D.R.P. 375658) that it decreases the inflammability of activated carbon—generally of pyrophorous nature.

The effect of ferric hydroxide on alumina was also investigated. No increase in efficiency was however observed. Ferric hydroxide in itself is also a poor decolourising agent.

The Effect of Temperature of Roasting and Water Contents of the Decolourisers.

It is desirable to investigate how far the activities of the above mixed adsorbents depend on the temperature of roasting and the consequent variation of water content. The literature in connection with the temperature to which an adsorbent should be heated for the purpose of proper activation is full of contradictory reports. Thus Parsons ("Fuller's Earth," 1913) does not recommend any heating at all for Fuller's earth, while Deckert (*Seifensied. Ztg.*, 1925, 52, 754) has obtained best results by heating Fuller's earth to 500°–600°. Munro and Johnson (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1925, 17, 88) recommend a temperature of 400° for alumina gel; Perry (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, 29, 1462) a temperature of 200°; while Dunstan and others (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1924, 43, 179T.) a temperature of 600° for bauxite.

Several investigators have also noted the rôle of water content adsorbents. Thus Patrick and McGavack (*loc. cit.*) have observed that a small amount of moisture is always associated with silica gel for efficient adsorption of sulphur dioxide and water vapour. Roy (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, 29, 75) has found that silica gel with 5% water displays the greatest activity for N_2O_4 . Munro and Johnson (*loc. cit.*) find the presence of 4.5–7% water in alumina necessary for best adsorption of gases and vapours. Similar results

showing the influence of water on adsorption in solid-liquid interface have also been observed in the case of floridin (Gurwitsch, "Scientific Principles of Petroleum Technology," p. 406).

The following table contains data of experiments conducted with a view to ascertain the rôle of temperature of roasting and water content in the adsorbents.

TABLE VIIA.

Variation of efficiency of bauxite with temperature of roasting and water content.

Adsorbent used—5 g. per 100 c.c. kerosene no. I, of red colour = 2.7° and yellow colour = 16.5°L.

Temperature of roasting.	Moisture remaining.	Red colour.		Yellow colour.	
		Colour obs.	Colour removed.	Colour obs.	Colour removed.
—	11.8 %	2.45°L	9.37%	15.0°L	9.09%
275°-300°	9.73	2.15	20.37	14.2	13.94
350°-400°	9.12	2.15	20.37	14.2	13.94
400°-500°	6.33	2.15	20.37	13.5	18.18
Strong ignition	—	2.15	20.37	13.5	18.18

TABLE VIIB.

Variation of efficiency of bauxite-silica II (silica, 21.66%) with temperature of roasting and water content.

Adsorbent used—5 g. per 100 c.c. kerosene no. I.

Temperature of roasting.	Moisture remaining.	Red colour.		Yellow colour.	
		Colour obs.	Colour removed.	Colour obs.	Colour removed.
60°	20.89%	1.6°L	40.74%	12.5°L	24.24%
150°	12.23	1.1	59.26	10.8	34.54
250°	9.23	1.0	62.96	9.8	40.61
275°-300°	7.58	1.0	62.96	9.8	40.61
400°-500°	5.95	0.92	65.93	9.8	40.61
Strong ignition	—	1.1	59.26	10.8	34.54

TABLE VIIC.

Variation of efficiency of alumina-silica III (silica, 63.3%) with temperature of roasting and water content.

Adsorbent used—2 g. per 100 c.c. kerosene no. I, of red colour = 2.7° and yellow colour = 16.5°L.

Temperature of roasting.	Water content.	<i>Red colour.</i>		<i>Yellow colour.</i>	
		Colour obs.	Colour removed.	Colour obs.	Colour removed.
60°	22.55%	1.6°L	40.74%	12.0°L	27.27%
150°	7.46	0.92	65.93	8.8	46.67
175°	4.27	0.92	65.93	7.6	53.94
250°	2.29	0.95	64.81	9.3	43.64
300°	1.87	1.1	59.26	9.3	43.64
Strong ignition	—	1.35	50.00	9.8	40.61

It will be seen from the above figures that completely dried adsorbents have less activity than partially dried ones. Thus the power of decolourisation attains a maximum with 6.33% of water in the case of bauxite, 5.95% in the optimum bauxite-silica mixture and 4.27% in the optimum alumina-silica mixture. The percentage of moisture content and temperature of roasting are interdependent. At any particular temperature it is very difficult even after prolonged drying to drive off more than a certain percentage of water and it seems as if an equilibrium is reached in the moisture content of each adsorbent.

Regeneration of Adsorbents.

The mixed adsorbents must be capable of repeated regeneration for industrial use. In this respect the inorganic decolourisers have an advantage over activated carbon and animal charcoal which in spite of their high decolourising value, are costly to revivify. We have regenerated the mixed adsorbents after ten successive treatments and found that the regenerated adsorbents have suffered only very slightly in their activity. The usual methods of treatment with steam and air has been found quite satisfactory. A preliminary treatment with water which is adsorbed in preference and drives out the major portion of the adsorbed material from the decolourisers has

also been found to give satisfactory results (*cf.* Gurwitsch, *loc. cit.*, p. 415). The mass is subsequently roasted in a current of air, or if the temperature is to be kept to the minimum possible level in a mixture of steam and air. It will be observed that after the first regeneration the activity of the mixed adsorbent slightly deteriorates, but further repeated regeneration has little injurious effect, if any. The decolouriser has been revived 10 times with little loss of efficiency. The experimental data are given in the following table:—

TABLE VIII.

Regeneration of the mixed decolouriser alumina-silica II.

Adsorbent—2 g. per 100 c.c. kerosene no. II, of red colour=1·6° and yellow colour=20°L.

No. of treatments.	<i>Red colour.</i>		<i>Yellow colour.</i>	
	Colour obs.	Colour removed.	Colour obs.	Colour removed.
1st	1·0°L	37·5%	13·0°L	35·0%
2nd	1·1	31·25	13·5	32·5
3rd	"	"	"	"
4th	"	"	"	"
5th	"	"	"	"
6th	"	"	"	"
7th	"	"	"	"
8th	"	"	"	"
9th	"	"	"	"
10th	"	"	14·2	29·0

Discussion.

It is generally agreed that adsorption is a physical phenomenon. As regards the mechanism of adsorption there are two principal theories. Zsigmondy, Patrick and other investigators maintain that adsorption is mainly due to capillary forces. In cases where the pores are of the nature of a cone, adsorption takes place at the narrow ends which are filled with the adsorbed substance, while the wider portions remained unoccupied. It may be imagined that in the mixed adsorbents the wider portions of the pores of one adsorbent are filled up

with another adsorbent deposited on it, thus forming a large number of narrow capillaries. This would also explain the fact that mechanical mixtures of the adsorbent have no increased efficiency. According to this theory, it would however be difficult to account for the fact that little or no increase of activity is noticed when iron hydroxide is precipitated on aluminium hydroxide. The chemical nature of the constituents evidently plays an important part. It will be noticed that best results are obtained when silica gel which is acidic in nature is deposited on alumina or bauxite of basic character.

The adsorption phenomenon have been explained in recent years by ordinary laws of molecular attraction (Eucken, *Verh. deut. physikal. Ges.*, 16, 349, *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1922, 28, 6; Polanyi, *Verh. deut. physikal. Ges.*, 1916, 18, 55; Lorenz and Lande, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1922, 125, 4). It is believed that this molecular attraction depends on the dipolar nature of most molecules. Dipolarity may also be induced in the molecules, of most substances, when they come under the influence of outside electric forces or in the proximity of other molecules. The intensity of attraction depends not only on the moments of the dipolar molecules coming within each other's influence, but also on the inclination which their axes form with one another. The adsorption potential depends on the distance of the dipolar molecules from the solid adsorbent surface, and on the angles which their axes build with the perpendicular on the adsorbent surface. These angles will naturally depend on the temperature, as the position of the axes will be disturbed by heat. In order to explain the comparatively small influence of temperature on adsorption, it is assumed that the forces of disturbance that would be caused by little differences in temperature, are very small in comparison with the forces of attraction.

Hence, the function of the adsorbent is mainly to expose a large surface and thus to provide a large number of molecules to influence the molecules of the material to be adsorbed. The electric properties of the adsorbent, such as its conductivity or dielectric constant would naturally have some influence on adsorption. But how far these electrical properties of different adsorbents affect the adsorption capacity is unfortunately extremely difficult to determine experimentally. It is not improbable that the presence of water in the adsorbents materially affect these electrical properties. It can easily be understood that the presence of large amounts of water will prevent the molecules of the adsorptive from coming in close

proximity with the molecules of the adsorbent, and hence the necessity for drying; but the complete absence of water will affect the above-mentioned electrical properties of the adsorbents and may injuriously affect the adsorption capacity. This may be a likely explanation for the presence of small amounts of water in the adsorbents, —a fact for which no satisfactory explanation is available.

In the mixed adsorbents it is reasonable to assume that narrow capillary canals are formed, the two walls of which are oppositely charged and therefore create an electric field within the pores, similar to electric condensers. Under the influence of this field the molecules of the adsorptive become dipolar and are therefore systematically arranged in the canals, thus increasing the amount of adsorption. When the walls are of the same charge the molecules attaching themselves to the surface will be similarly charged, and will repel one another, when in close proximity. They will therefore diminish the forces of adsorption or prevent other molecules from coming in to fill up the intervening space. The case is however different when the walls are of opposite charges. As the adsorbed molecules are now oppositely charged no repulsion takes place and other dipolar molecules will be attracted to fill up the intervening space, if any. Thus in Fig. VI, where both the walls are of the same charge, the

Fig. VI.

Fig. VII.

dipolar molecules attaching to the surfaces will each be positively charged. These molecules will repel each other or prevent the filling up of intervening space by other molecules. In Fig. VII, where the walls are oppositely charged the molecules attaching themselves to the walls will also be oppositely charged. Other dipolar molecules will therefore be attracted to fill up the intervening space and the axes of all the adsorbed molecules will be systematically arranged and the adsorption capacity will increase.

In conclusion, our best thanks are due to the Director of Geological Survey, Calcutta, for kindly supplying us with bauxite from the Central Provinces for the purpose of these experiments.